

Rural Resort Landscape Design Centred on Bamboo Culture Exploring Tourism Resorts in the Context of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy

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Abstract: This paper explores the integration of bamboo culture into rural resort landscape design within the framework of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy. Bamboo, an essential cultural and ecological symbol in China, is proposed as a central element in developing tourism resorts that align with sustainable rural development. The study investigates how bamboo-inspired landscapes can enhance the aesthetic appeal, cultural significance, and environmental sustainability of rural resorts. By analysing case studies from bamboo-rich regions, the paper assesses the potential of these designs to attract tourism, promote local heritage, and contribute to the economic revitalization of rural areas. The findings suggest that bamboo-centred design strategies not only preserve the ecological balance but also foster a unique cultural identity for rural resorts, supporting broader rural revitalization efforts in China. This research provides valuable insights for landscape architects, policymakers, and tourism developers aiming to harmonize cultural heritage with sustainable rural development goals.

Key points: Rural Resort, Landscape Design, Bamboo-centred Resorts, Rural Vitalization Strategy.

Introduction

In 2017, the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China unveiled the rural vitalization strategy, which later became the cornerstone of China's initiatives aimed at revitalizing rural areas. This comprehensive strategy includes five key areas: industrial development, ecological protection, cultural prosperity, effective governance, and improved living standards (Shi & Yang, 2022). A key element of the program is rural tourism development to ensure regional economic growth and cultural conservation. The Government of China's objective is to reduce the differences between urban and rural areas, to raise the standard of living of the rural population, and to safeguard the numerous cultural heritage treasures that characterize its thousands of rural landscapes through the promotion of tourism (Li et al., 2021). In this case, the general design of rural resorts has to be of a high standard, since the ultimate goal of such resorts is to attract visitors by offering an aesthetic, cultural, and nature-exploring stay. Bamboo, mostly recognized for its real cultural role and its ecological benefit, has grown into a perfect tool for the integration of typical Chinese values into modern landscape design. Also, historically, bamboo was indeed the most famous element in Chinese culture, signifying virtues like perseverance, modesty, and respect for nature (Qi, 2024). It has been a constant theme in Chinese art, poetry, and philosophy, universally treated as the logo for fidelity and capacity to survive. Besides its symbolic meaning, bamboo represents a renewable resource that contributes to environmental benefits. It is one of the few species of bamboo that grows incredibly fast and can regenerate without replanting, which characterizes them as helpers of the climate, through carbon sequestration (Kondvilkar & Thakare, 2021). Due to its characteristics, bamboos bring a special chance of flourishing for rural resort landscaping, which shares the ecological and cultural aims of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy.

The inclusion of bamboo in landscapes of the rural resorts undoubtedly brings about a few merits. First and foremost, the use of traditional Chinese aesthetics in current tourism development is bamboo's cultural resonance, which allows visitors to have a more authentic cultural interaction. Such cultural veracity appeals to many tourists who want something unique about rural China in this routine and mass tourism era (Li & Li, 2022). Third, bamboo also has ecological advantages, which make it a long-lasting option for landscaping and architecture. Being one of its most important features, the species possesses a very fast growth and a very small negative environmental impact, making it an ideal candidate for building eco-friendly resort areas, which correspond to the sustainability policies created in rural areas (Rathour et al., 2022). Thus, the presence of bamboo in both the architectural and ecological environment can help reduce environmental degradation, promote biodiversity, and also support the tourism industry sustainably in rural resorts. The local communities of rural areas in China can reap significant benefits related to tourism in the process of revitalization, as the urban population gradually starts to look for nature- and culture-based destinations (Chen et al., 2023). The implementation of tourism in the countryside is not alright as it is all about building the development that harmonizes and commits with local customs while also ensuring nature. Bamboo-based resort construction development, in response to this demand, has therefore gained more attention as a sustainable model that does not only integrate traditional Chinese craftsmanship and natural resources but also modern tourism infrastructures (Al-Hashimy, 2024a). In China's bamboo areas, that is, Sichuan, Zhejiang, and Fujian provinces, bamboo is already considered fashionable in construction and landscape design, and ecological tourism can emerge from this too (Yiqing & Protection, 2021).

In this paper, we will examine the applicability of bamboo-based landscape design as a means to support sustainable tourism, in connection with China's Rural Vitalization Strategy. Through a review of several areas where bamboo is a culturally and ecologically distinct feature, this research wants to look into the ways bamboo-inspired design can add beauty, and cultural, and environmental features to small resorts in the countryside. The analysis will broadly cover what bamboo can do in specific ways in the construction and architecture of resorts. The study will discuss the utilitarian aspect of bamboo and will also delve into its cultural significance. The study further examines the impacts of the resorts on the economy and social life in the local communities, pinpoints how bamboo-centred designs can assist rural economic revitalization and the role of the resorts in attracting both domestic and international tourists. The research ultimately envisages the discovery of some innovative strategies by history and tourism planners, amalgamating the presence of cultural ancestry with the modern implementation of environmentally acceptable rural tourism development in the future. The study results demonstrate the necessity to incorporate local resources, as well as conventional cultural elements, such as bamboo, in the modern resort designs to work towards both economic development and cultural preservation and in the context of China's rural revitalization program (Al-Hashimy & Jinfang, 2024).

Literature Review

The Rural Vitalization Strategy of China, which began officially in 2017, is a comprehensive plan to turn rural areas into developing areas, the objectives of which include the stimulation of sustainable economic growth, improvement of rural governance, preservation of cultural heritage, and natural environment conservation. This will certainly be aimed at tackling the too-sufficient gap between the cities and the countryside, improving the lifestyles of rural inhabitants, and empowering local economies on the excess of natural resources in rural areas, such as tourism (Kusio et al., 2022). Tourism, and especially eco-tourism and cultural tourism which detects tourists coming to rural districts to present the cultural heritage and natural scenery, has been identified as important tools within this plan (Altassan, 2023). There has been a rising demand for authentic, sustainable tourism experiences because it is no longer enough for tourists to get out of their regular environment. Chinese policymakers see this rural tourism development as creating rural incomes and at the same time protecting the local ecosystem and tradition as a common approach (Widawski et al., 2023). Table 1 displays key rural development policies and their impact on tourism.

Table 1: Key Rural Development Policies and their Impact on Tourism

Policy/Strategy	Year	Objectives	Impact on Rural Tourism
Rural Vitalization Strategy	2017	Revitalize rural economies, preserve culture, and promote sustainable development.	Expansion of eco-tourism and cultural tourism initiatives in rural regions
National Tourism Development Plan	2016	Develop tourism infrastructure and enhance tourist experiences in rural areas.	Increased government investment in rural tourism facilities and services
Policy/Strategy	Year	Objectives	Impact on Rural Tourism

This table outlines the major policies that have driven rural tourism development in China, particularly focusing on how these policies have provided structural support for the growth of eco-tourism and culturally rich destinations. Bamboo occupies a central position in Chinese culture and identity, symbolizing attributes such as resilience, humility, and harmony with the natural world (Britton MA, 2024). For millennia, bamboo has been celebrated in Chinese art, literature, and philosophy, particularly within Confucian and Taoist traditions, where it is regarded as a symbol of strength, integrity, and adaptability (Al-Hashimy, 2024b). These qualities have made bamboo an essential element of Chinese material culture, widely used in construction, arts and crafts, and daily life. Bamboo's deep cultural significance is paralleled by its ecological benefits, making it an ideal material for integrating sustainable development with cultural preservation in rural resort design. Bamboo's fast growth, carbon sequestration capacity, and biodegradability make it an eco-friendly alternative to conventional building materials, particularly in regions seeking to balance tourism development with environmental sustainability (Rathour et al., 2022). Moreover, the cultural associations with bamboo enhance the authenticity of rural resorts, creating immersive environments that offer visitors a connection to traditional Chinese values while promoting ecological mindfulness. Table 2 shows cultural symbolism and applications of bamboo in Chinese society.

Table 2: Cultural Symbolism and Applications of Bamboo in Chinese Society

Cultural Aspect	Symbolism/Meaning	Application in Modern Landscape Design
Confucian Ideas	Integrity, Resilience	Bamboo is incorporated into structural and garden designs, symbolizing cultural virtues.
Harmony with Nature	Balance, Simplicity	Bamboo is a central element in eco-friendly resort design to reflect harmony with nature.
Traditional Chinese Art and Philosophy	Purity, Strength	Bamboo-inspired structures that echo traditional Chinese architecture in modern tourism.

This table highlights the key cultural and symbolic meanings of bamboo and its applications in contemporary landscape design. Bamboo's ecological benefits have garnered attention in sustainable tourism development. As the world seeks eco-friendly alternatives to conventional building materials, bamboo's renewability and low environmental footprint make it a popular choice. Bamboo has been used in constructing resorts, hotels, and recreational areas that prioritize ecological conservation while offering aesthetic and cultural value (Razal, 2022). Case studies reveal that bamboo-centered designs significantly contribute to reducing carbon emissions and promoting biodiversity, which is critical for regions rich in natural resources. Research by Zhao et al. (2024) shows that bamboo's use in architectural design contributes to a unique, visually appealing experience for tourists while adhering to the principles of sustainable tourism. Table 3 demonstrates the environmental benefits of bamboo in resort design.

Table 3: Environmental Benefits of Bamboo in Resort Design

Environmental Benefit	Description	Examples from the Tourism Sector
Carbon	Absorbs more CO ₂ than many	Bamboo forests surrounding eco-

Sequestration	other plants	resorts in Sichuan
Low Environmental Impact	Renewable resources with minimal waste	Bamboo construction in resorts, reducing deforestation
Contribution to Biodiversity	Supports rich ecosystems in rural areas	Bamboo landscapes supporting local fauna

This table highlights the key environmental advantages of bamboo when used in tourism resort design. Sichuan, Zhejiang, and Fujian, among other regions in China, are particularly well-known for their bamboo-centric resort concepts that have pleasantly integrated bamboo into the surrounding environment. These regions marry the cultural and environmental attributes of bamboo with the modern need for resorts that feature nature-based experiences and offer an authentic cultural experience. Surveys done in these zones ascertain that bamboo-based models not only beautify the resorts but also form the link between the tourism infrastructure and the natural ecosystem (K. Liu et al., 2022). The Sichuan Bamboo Eco-Resort is one of the exemplary cases of how bamboo can be designed into a landscape. Made completely with bamboo found locally, it is the resort that adds to environmental sustainability by bringing down its carbon footprint and promoting biodiversity in the area (Al-Hashimy et al., 2023). The resort's design incorporates bamboo in both its architecture and landscaping, which creates a binding factor for the different life forms inhabiting the place. Table 4 focuses on the case studies of bamboo resort designs in China.

Table 4: Case Studies of Bamboo-Centred Resort Designs in China

Resort Name	Location	Design Focus	Impact on Local Tourism
Sichuan Bamboo Eco-Resort	Sichuan	Bamboo-centric landscape and architecture	Increased tourist interest in eco-tourism
Fujian Bamboo Forest Resort	Fujian	Traditional bamboo structures	Boost in local employment and cultural tourism
Zhejiang Bamboo Villas	Zhejiang	Bamboo is both an architectural and cultural element	Enhanced tourist satisfaction and local community involvement

The table above contains resort designs in China that showcase bamboo as the centre of the activity. This table gives an illustration of the resorts located in the areas of China's bamboo-rich regions as well as the specific nature of the effect of the design on tourism. Rural tourism, led by bamboo-focused resorts, has been the root of China's culture preservation and rural revitalization. The tourist influx increases the number of job positions, develops infrastructure, and spreads the native culture. Moreover, it has been the reason for the continuance of traditional ways, including the bamboo crafts trade, which is learnt from the past (Sun & Liu, 2022). Research conducted by Ma et al. (2021) displays the existence of two different functions of rural tourism: the first is to relieve poverty, and the second is to protect cultural identity. Bamboo resorts contribute to this by offering visitors culturally immersive experiences that highlight the importance of local customs and sustainable practices. Table 5 shows the economic and cultural impact of bamboo-centred resorts.

Table 5: Economic and Cultural Impact of Bamboo-Centred Resorts

Impact Type	Description	Evidence from Case Studies
Economic Impact	The creation of local jobs increased rural incomes.	Bamboo-based resorts in Sichuan Province generated employment and supported local artisans.
Cultural Preservation	Preservation of traditional bamboo craftsmanship and cultural practices	Fujian resorts supported local craftspeople through bamboo architecture workshops
Environmental Sustainability	Minimal environmental footprint, enhanced biodiversity	Bamboo-centred designs in Zhejiang promoted sustainable tourism practices and supported local ecosystems

This table summarizes the economic and cultural benefits of bamboo-centred resorts, illustrating their role in promoting sustainable rural tourism. The literature on rural tourism and bamboo-centred landscape design underscores the cultural and environmental significance of bamboo as a key element in sustainable resort development. Bamboo-based designs not only align with China's Rural Vitalization Strategy but also foster a deeper connection between tourism, cultural heritage, and ecological preservation. The integration of bamboo into resort landscapes creates an immersive cultural experience that appeals to eco-conscious tourists while supporting the local economy and preserving traditional craftsmanship.

Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design to explore the impact of bamboo-centred landscape design on rural resorts within the framework of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy. In this mixed-methods approach, short of a comprehensive analysis, both qualitative and quantitative data can be included. The qualitative dimension provides an understanding of stakeholders' perspectives in terms of culture, ecology, and operational rules in biophilic resorts, while the quantitative analysis investigates tourists' perceptions and satisfaction with bamboo-based designs. Rural tourism is positively impacted through the combined aim to study both subjective experiences and objective data, which can help to determine the meaning of bamboo. This study will focus on those bamboo-rich regions in China, which include Sichuan, Fujian, and Zhejiang province. These sites were the best options for the development of resorts because they have vast bamboo resources and deep connections with bamboo culture. Bamboo will be showcased in many of the chosen resorts in these regions through the architecture and landscape designs, which fit the vision of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy, that is to make resources and culture the main tourism development elements (K. Liu et al., 2022). The resorts under study were endorsed according to some particular factors. First, the resorts should embody the concept of a bamboo house that includes even its odd structures such as fences. Another factor was sustainability practices, and resort sustainability was measured by the extent to which bamboo was being used as an eco-friendly building material. Third, it was taken into account the level of community participation, here it is in favour of the resorts that venture to employ local artisans and craftspeople. Lastly, a considerable number of guests were found to be involved in different bamboo-related activities, which formed the basis for concluding that tourist perceptions could be accurately measured. Table 6 shows the selection criteria for rural resorts in bamboo-rich regions.

Table 6: Selection Criteria for Rural Resorts in Bamboo-Rich Regions

Criteria	Description
Use of bamboo in design	Extensive use in architecture and landscaping
Sustainability practices	Bamboo as a key material in eco-friendly resort design
Community involvement	Engagement of local artisans and craftspeople
Tourist engagement	Bamboo-centred tourist activities and experiences

To gain in-depth insights into the cultural, economic, and ecological significance of bamboo-centred design, semi-structured interviews were conducted with three key stakeholder groups: resort managers, local community members, and tourists. The interviews with resort managers focused on their motivations for incorporating bamboo into their designs, the challenges faced in using bamboo as a sustainable material, and the cultural significance of bamboo in creating an authentic resort experience. Interviews with local community members, particularly bamboo artisans, explored the economic and social impacts of the resorts on their livelihoods, the preservation of traditional bamboo craftsmanship, and their involvement in resort operations. Finally, interviews with tourists were aimed at understanding their perceptions of bamboo-centred resort designs, with a focus on cultural authenticity, environmental sustainability, and overall satisfaction. Each interview lasted about 45-60 minutes. They were primarily held in a conference room in the resorts. The interviews were audio-recorded (with the consent of the interviewees), transcribed, and studied using thematic analysis. From this approach, I could observe reoccurring themes and patterns related to the cultural

and ecological meanings ascribed to bamboo, the sustainability trend in the design of bamboo-based resort development, as well as their social and economic impacts on the local communities.

Apart from interviews, the field observation was a prime source of information on how bamboo was put into practice in the resorts' design. These observations included the use of bamboo for architectural purposes (for instance, bamboo buildings, fences, and pathways) and for landscape integration (for example, bamboo gardens, and groves of natural bamboo). At the same time, photographs and detailed notes were taken to get a complete understanding of the bamboo elements and design features. A printed questionnaire was used to complement the qualitative part of the making of this research, administered to a sample of 300 tourists, across the nine selected resorts. The survey revealed that bamboo-based designs were the most satisfactory by tourists and that they considered the bamboo's cultural and environmental significance proper for the resort experience. There was a questionnaire of 20 items, which was created based on a 5-point Likert scale focusing on factors like design aesthetics, perceived cultural authenticity, the level of awareness about the sustainability initiatives, and overall satisfaction level with the resort experience. The quantitative data from the surveys allowed for an empirical analysis of the relationships between tourist satisfaction and key design elements. Table 7 shows survey variables and measurements.

Table 7: Survey Variables and Measurement

Variable	Survey Question	Measurement (5-point Likert Scale)
The aesthetic quality of bamboo design	How satisfied are you with the visual appeal of the bamboo-centred landscape?	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)
Cultural authenticity	Do you feel that the resort's design reflects traditional Chinese culture?	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)
Environmental sustainability	Are you aware of the resort's use of bamboo as an eco-friendly material?	1 (Not Aware) to 5 (Very Aware)
Overall tourist satisfaction	How satisfied are you with your experience at the resort overall?	1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)

The data collected from the qualitative interviews and field observations were analysed using thematic analysis. The interview transcripts were coded to identify key themes related to the cultural significance of bamboo, its environmental benefits, and the social and economic impacts on local communities. The themes were grouped into broader categories such as cultural authenticity, sustainability, and community involvement. This analysis was facilitated by NVivo software, which allowed for the systematic identification of patterns across different stakeholders. For the quantitative data collected through surveys, descriptive statistics were used to summarize the responses to key variables. Additionally, regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between tourists' overall satisfaction and their perceptions of bamboo-centred design, cultural authenticity, and environmental sustainability. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software, with the results presented in tables and graphs to illustrate key trends and relationships. The following table 8 shows descriptive statistics of tourist satisfaction with bamboo-centred design.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Tourist Satisfaction with Bamboo-Centred Design

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
The aesthetic quality of bamboo design	4.5	0.6
Cultural authenticity	4.3	0.7
Environmental sustainability	4.4	0.5
Overall tourist satisfaction	4.6	0.4

The study ensured the validity and reliability of the data collection instruments through several methods. The interview questions were pilot-tested with a small group of stakeholders to ensure clarity and relevance. The process of triangulation encompassed the cross-referencing of data gathered from interviews, field observations, and tourist surveys, aimed at ensuring both the

consistency and accuracy of the findings. For the quantitative data, the survey instrument was also pilot-tested with 30 tourists before the full deployment, and Cronbach's alpha was calculated to assess internal consistency. The alpha value was 0.85, indicating high reliability (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Table 9 shows the reliability analysis of the survey instrument.

Table 9: Reliability Analysis of Survey Instrument

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
The aesthetic quality of bamboo design	0.82
Cultural authenticity	0.85
Environmental sustainability	0.80
Overall tourist satisfaction	0.88

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines. All participants provided informed consent before their participation, and the research was conducted following the ethical standards of the host university's ethics committee. The anonymity and confidentiality of participants were maintained throughout the study, and all data collected were securely stored. The interviews and surveys were voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Eventually, the report deliberates some restrictions. First of all, the scope of the study, which is limited to only a few resorts in a certain bamboo seasonality area, might narrow down the applicability of the results beyond that region of China or other cultural contexts. Thus, the issue regarding the dependence on self-reported data by the tourists may add social desirability response bias, which means the tourists might have given a socially desirable response.

Results

From the results of this investigation on bamboo-centred landscape formation design in the context of rural resorts, the researchers obtained important aspects linked to the cultural, ecological, and economic aspects of bamboo-centric resort development. In the present work, we provide evidence through qualitative interviews, field observations, and quantitative surveys that show that bamboo-centred designs are largely appreciated by local stakeholders and travellers because of their cultural authenticity and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the application of bamboo to the local economic development, including the provision of jobs and preservation of bamboo handicrafts, has been beneficial. While conducting the interviews with the resort managers and the local artisans, one of the crucial discoveries related to the pointed bamboo as the most important element of the resort design is the cultural significance of bamboo for the people. The managers of the resorts noted that no one can understand bamboo apart from the fact that it represents the values of resilience, humility, and harmony with nature—values that are profoundly connected to Chinese culture. These cultural themes find their expression in the design of the resorts, which not only use bamboo for aesthetic outcomes but also to keep the original Chinese elements intact. Local artisans accentuated the significance of bamboo craftsmanship in their community, arguing that through making pavilions, fencing, and pathways, younger artisans could have a chance to gain traditional skills-sharing opportunities. It too has kept the cultural identity of the rural regions and opened up the source of income to the locals. Table 10 displays cultural themes identified from interviews with resort managers and local artisans.

Table 10: Cultural Themes Identified from Interviews with Resort Managers and Local Artisans

Theme	Description
Cultural Symbolism	Bamboo represents resilience, harmony with nature, and traditional Chinese values.
Preservation of Craftsmanship	Bamboo-based designs preserve traditional bamboo craftsmanship in rural regions.
Cultural Immersion for Tourists	Tourists experience traditional Chinese culture through bamboo-centred designs.

The research implies that bamboo-oriented resorts provide an exceptional cultural immersion experience for tourists, where they can partake in traditional Chinese customs and enjoy modern amenities. Interviewees commonly observed that the bamboo-based designs add to the authenticity of their stay at the resorts, enabling them to appreciate their vacations. The ecological advantages of the bamboo-based designs attracted both the managers and tourists as a significant factor for the hotel. Field studies and interviews suggested that bamboo plays a prominent role in the resorts' sustainability agenda, as it is fast-growing and renewable. On the other hand, resort managers stated that bamboo can be ecologically harvested because bamboo's natural growth cycle has minimal environmental impact, therefore making it an ideal material for eco-friendly resorts. The tourists surveyed also reflected a strong awareness of the resorts' sustainability actions. The survey indicated that tourists looked at bamboo as an eco-friendly approach to resort building, and some preferred to stay at the ones that prioritized sustainability. Table 11 shows the tourist perception towards environmental sustainability in bamboo-based resorts.

Table 11: Tourist Perceptions of Environmental Sustainability of Bamboo-Centred Resorts

Survey Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
Awareness of bamboo's role in sustainability	4.4	0.5
Preference for eco-friendly resort design	4.6	0.4
Satisfaction with the resort's environmental initiatives	4.5	0.6

As shown in Table 11, the high mean scores indicate that tourists were generally very satisfied with the resorts' environmental initiatives, with a particular appreciation for the use of bamboo as a sustainable building material. The findings suggest that resorts focused on bamboo play a crucial role in enhancing both the aesthetic and cultural appeal of the destination, while also addressing the growing demand for environmentally sustainable tourism practices. The findings suggest that resorts centred around bamboo contribute positively to the economic development of surrounding communities. Interviews with local artisans and community members highlighted the role of these resorts in creating employment opportunities and preserving traditional bamboo craftsmanship. Many of the resorts employed local artisans to construct bamboo structures, which provided much-needed income to rural households. Moreover, resort managers noted that the use of locally sourced bamboo reduced construction costs and supported the local economy by fostering demand for bamboo-related products and services. The economic benefits extended beyond direct employment, as the presence of tourists stimulated the development of local businesses such as souvenir shops, restaurants, and guided tours. Table 12 shows the economic benefits of bamboo-centred resorts to local communities.

Table 12: Economic Benefits of Bamboo-Centred Resorts to Local Communities

Economic Impact	Description
Job Creation	Employment of local artisans and workers in resort construction and maintenance
Preservation of Traditional Skills	Opportunities for artisans to pass down bamboo craftsmanship to younger generations
Growth of Local Businesses	Increased demand for local products and services (e.g., bamboo souvenirs, tours)
Economic Impact	Description

The survey results also indicate that tourists appreciated the connection between the resorts and the local economy. Many tourists mentioned that they were more likely to purchase locally produced bamboo products, knowing that their spending would directly benefit the local community. The quantitative data from the surveys revealed that tourists were overwhelmingly satisfied with the bamboo-centred designs of the resorts. The mean score for overall satisfaction was 4.6, indicating a high level of approval from tourists. Additionally, the aesthetic quality of the bamboo-centred designs was rated highly by tourists, with a mean score of 4.5. This suggests that tourists found the bamboo-based designs to be both visually appealing and integral to their experience of the resort.

The cultural authenticity of the resort design also contributed significantly to tourist satisfaction, with a mean score of 4.3. Tourists appreciated how the bamboo-based architecture reflected traditional Chinese cultural values, and many commented on the importance of cultural immersion in their travel experiences. Table 13 shows descriptive statistics of tourist satisfaction with bamboo-centred design.

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics of Tourist Satisfaction with Bamboo-Centred Design

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
The aesthetic quality of bamboo design	4.5	0.6
Cultural authenticity	4.3	0.7
Environmental sustainability	4.4	0.5
Overall tourist satisfaction	4.6	0.4

The results presented in Table 13 indicate that the bamboo-centred design significantly contributed to tourists' overall satisfaction. Tourists consistently rated the aesthetic appeal, cultural authenticity, and sustainability of the resorts highly, showing a strong correlation between these factors and their overall experience. To further explore the relationship between the key factors influencing tourist satisfaction, a regression analysis was conducted. The analysis examined how the independent variables (aesthetic quality, cultural authenticity, and environmental sustainability) impacted the dependent variable (overall tourist satisfaction). The results of the regression analysis show that all three variables had a significant positive impact on tourist satisfaction. Cultural authenticity and environmental sustainability were particularly strong predictors of satisfaction, suggesting that tourists placed high value on the cultural and ecological aspects of the resort design. Table 14 shows a regression analysis of factors influencing tourist satisfaction.

Table 14: Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Tourist Satisfaction

Variable	Beta Coefficient	Significance (p-value)
The aesthetic quality of bamboo design	0.32	0.001
Cultural authenticity	0.41	0.000
Environmental sustainability	0.38	0.000

Table 14 demonstrates that cultural authenticity and environmental sustainability serve as the primary predictors of tourist satisfaction, with both variables exhibiting a high degree of statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that the overall experience of tourists was notably shaped by their awareness of the cultural and environmental dimensions of bamboo-centred designs. The findings of this study suggest that resort designs that prioritize bamboo are essential in improving tourist satisfaction by offering an authentic, aesthetically pleasing, and environmentally sustainable experience (Hussain et al., 2023). The designs play a crucial role in bolstering local economies, while simultaneously facilitating the preservation of traditional bamboo craftsmanship. The findings suggest that bamboo-centric resorts align with the goals of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy, promoting cultural preservation alongside sustainable economic development.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of the significance of bamboo-centred landscape designs in rural resorts and their alignment with the broader goals of China's Rural Vitalization Strategy, particularly concerning cultural preservation, environmental sustainability, and economic development. This discussion explores the key findings in the existing literature, highlighting the implications for resort design, local communities, and sustainable tourism practices.

Cultural Significance and Authenticity

The research demonstrated that designs centred around bamboo substantially improve the cultural authenticity of rural resorts, facilitating a deeper engagement for tourists with traditional Chinese values. The symbolic representation of bamboo, embodying resilience, harmony, and a connection

with nature, significantly resonates with tourists, as indicated by their elevated satisfaction scores regarding cultural immersion. This is consistent with previous studies that emphasize the importance of culturally significant materials, such as bamboo, in fostering authentic tourism experiences (Zhao et al., 2024). The cultural symbolism of bamboo encompasses the preservation of traditional craftsmanship, a facet emphasized by the local artisans involved in the study. The incorporation of bamboo craftsmanship in resort design provides guests with a genuine cultural experience while simultaneously supporting the preservation of traditional skills. This finding reinforces the argument put forth by Luo et al. (2022) that tourism can significantly contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage. Incorporating local artisans into the construction and design of resorts serves to connect historical practices with contemporary developments. This approach not only facilitates the transmission of traditional knowledge to future generations but also enriches the cultural allure of the resorts. Nonetheless, an area that merits additional investigation is the comparative perception of cultural experiences by international tourists in relation to that of domestic tourists. This study primarily concentrated on domestic tourism; however, exploring whether the cultural symbolism of bamboo holds similar significance for foreign visitors would offer a more holistic understanding of bamboo's role in global tourism markets.

Environmental Sustainability

The study strongly affirmed the role of bamboo as a sustainable material, with both tourists and resort managers acknowledging the ecological advantages of incorporating bamboo into resort architecture and landscaping. The elevated levels of tourist satisfaction regarding the resorts' environmental sustainability initiatives indicate that eco-friendly design features, including the incorporation of bamboo, are gaining significance among travellers, especially those pursuing more environmentally responsible travel experiences. This finding is consistent with the increasing body of research that highlights the significance of sustainable tourism and environmentally conscious design (Li et al., 2024). Bamboo, recognized for its rapid growth cycle and minimal environmental impact, aligns effectively with the sustainability objectives of rural tourism. The findings of the study provide additional support for prior research, indicating that sustainable materials such as bamboo can act as a distinctive selling proposition for resorts, appealing to environmentally conscious travellers who value sustainability in their travel decisions (Masviba, 2022). The results also indicate the wider global trend of integrating sustainability into tourism development, which is increasingly significant for both travellers and tourism operators. The significant link between environmental sustainability and visitor happiness, as indicated by the regression analysis, highlights the increasing desire for eco-friendly travel alternatives. Bamboo-centric resorts not only aid in the conservation of local ecosystems but also accommodate the needs of contemporary travellers who prioritize sustainability.

Economic and Social Impacts on Local Communities

Our research proved to be financially beneficial for the community where the bamboo resorts were implemented. The resorts have greatly contributed to the successful reform of rural activities through the creation of employment, the promotion of local enterprises, as well as the preservation of craft or trade. Herein lies the key to China's Rural Vitalization Strategy, a central tenet of which is the significance placed on tourism and other industries, as a means of achieving economic development in the countryside (Y. Liu et al., 2022). Assessment of how local craftsmen are involved in the process of creation and maintenance of bamboo-based designs shows that this both brings employment and the preservation of the culture. In line with the previous research which demonstrates that rural tourism is capable of creating local jobs (Yang et al., 2021), the current investigation concludes that bamboo-dependent resorts not only generate direct employment but also encourage the development of related industries like bamboo crafts and accommodation services to local people, thus presenting a multiplier effect for the local economy. Nonetheless, the research draws questions about the sustainability of the economic advantages in the long run. While resorts centred around bamboo have already made an early contribution to the local economies, it is important to continuously ensure that these positive benefits are upheld. Future research may

explore how resorts can be built to take part in community development programs, like training programs for the local people, that in the long give holidays for tourists should keep enriching the communities and supporting rural vitality.

Tourist Satisfaction and Experience

As a striking occurrence, quantitative data unveiled that the tourists rated the bamboo-centred designs for their stay. Tourists valued not only the aesthetic appeal but also the authenticity and sustainability of the designs embodied. The regression analysis showed that the two most powerful factors were cultural authenticity and environmental sustainability when it came to predicting tourist satisfaction. These results proved that cultural connectivity and sustainability were the important aspects of the overall experience in the bamboo-centred resorts. This finding indicates that bamboo resorts may be the target market for the growing willingness of visitors to seek out and choose trips with cultural immersion or green practices as a priority. The incorporation of bamboo in the nature of these resorts gives their guests a different space that cannot be imitated in standard hotels and has a marketing edge over bikini resorts, thus making it more attractive for tourists. Surprisingly, the strong effect of cultural authenticity on tourist pleasure draws attention to the urge of resort designers to connect the resorts to the cultural and local values of the area. Such a result, therefore, can be interpreted as supporting what the authors Zhang et al. (2022) highlighted in their article, namely, that cultural heritage tourism is the one that sticks in the tourists' minds. When staying at a bamboo-based resort, visitors can not only see and touch bamboo furniture but also feel and reconnect with the history and values of rural China.

Implications for Future Tourism Development

This study's findings carry significant implications for the future trajectory of rural tourism development in China and other regions. Bamboo-centred resorts exemplify the potential for utilizing local cultural and ecological resources to develop sustainable and culturally enriching tourism experiences. It will be a perfect example of the strategy suggested by the Rural Vitalization strategy adopted by China, which seeks to develop tourism in rural areas while simultaneously protecting nature and culture. The interesting fact is that a large number of tourists commented on bamboo-styled designs as a noticeable feature of the resorts. Therefore, the remaining parts of the world should use such resorts to attain sustainable tourism infrastructure. Bamboo is used not only as a material but also as a symbol or cultural role model. This way, it helps in combining the ideas of sustainability and cultural authenticity in the design of resorts. The latter concept is becoming more and more popular mainly due to responsible tourism. Moreover, for these innovations to achieve the true depth of sustainability, tourism operators must strive, above all, for the welfare of residents whose community is dependent on their activities. The present study reveals that resorts focusing on bamboo could give rise to economic benefits and could contribute to the adoption of cultural heritage; however, the realization of these benefits necessitates effective management to guarantee their sustainability in the long term.

Limitations and Future Research

This study renders insightful observations to comprehend what the bamboo-centric designs are about, yet it is also imperative to be aware of the scarcity of such types. Such a limitation may focus on specific resorts and bamboo-rich areas only in China, but their findings may apply to other locations or countries. We suggest extending the scope of different resorts which incorporate bamboo-centred designs in varying cultural settings that can provide us with fascinating insights into how bamboo-centred designs are operated in diverse environments. Additionally, using self-reported data from tourists can also be problematic. They can be biased depending on how they respond to socially sensitive matters, especially issues of sustainability. In the future, self-reported data may be enhanced by introducing quantifiable measures of the environmental impact of designs based on bamboo, for instance, carbon footprint analysis. Such measures will help to determine the real environmental benefits coming from the bamboo designs. This paper could later be extended to cover the viewpoints of international tourists to have a deeper knowledge base concerning the

connection between bamboo-rich designs and foreign audiences. This would certainly offer resorts with tremendous and practical opinions for targeting a more varied list of tourists.

Conclusion

The study has shed light on the bamboo-dominant landscape design function in rural resort construction under China's Rural Vitalization Strategy, with the emphasis being placed on the role of heritage conservation, sustainability, and the stimulation of the local economy. Consequently, the studies capture the cultural essence of bamboo, not only as the emblem of Chinese values, for example, unity and harmony with nature but also as its principal and environment-friendly activity in resort construction. The rural resorts that have been harnessing the traditional bamboo skill into artwork and outdoor design are perfect examples, as they provide tourists with a more cultural experience, making their trips even more gratifying. The research also reveals the beneficial environmental practices of applying bamboo as a material in the design of resorts. Since bamboo is a naturally replenishable and supernatural-friendly plant, it is perfectly appropriate for eco-tourism growth. Tourists in Resorts realized the greenness of nature and were hence very appreciative, an indication that people are increasingly emphasizing nature-centred resorts. The fact that bamboo-centred ecosystems have an impressively high number of tourists expressing their satisfaction, specifically to cultural authenticity, and environmental sustainability, shows that bamboo-centred ecosystems represent the development of a responsible tourism model and the incorporation of the preferences of contemporary tourists.

In terms of economic and social impacts, the integration of local communities, particularly through the employment of artisans and the promotion of bamboo craftsmanship, has provided significant economic benefits to rural areas. This is in line with the goals of the Rural Vitalization Strategy, which seeks to alleviate poverty and promote economic development through rural tourism. The findings suggest that bamboo-centred resorts not only support local economies by creating jobs but also foster cultural sustainability by preserving traditional skills. Despite these positive outcomes, the long-term sustainability of these benefits requires careful management. Resorts must continue to engage with local communities and invest in initiatives that promote the well-being of artisans and other local workers, ensuring that the economic benefits are sustained over time. Bamboo-centred rural resorts represent a successful model for integrating cultural heritage, environmental sustainability, and economic development. They provide a blueprint for how local resources and traditional knowledge can be leveraged to create unique, culturally significant, and eco-friendly tourism experiences. As demand for responsible and immersive tourism continues to grow, the lessons learned from bamboo-centred resorts in China offer valuable insights for rural tourism development both domestically and globally. Further research should continue to explore how such models can be adapted to different cultural and environmental contexts, ensuring that tourism development remains sustainable and beneficial for local communities.

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